

Codebook: Motivations and Challenges in Software Engineering

	Aggregate Dimension	Second-Order Theme	Definition
Motivation to Software Engineering	Intrinsic Motivation	Personal Enjoyment	Finding satisfaction or pleasure from engaging with something one genuinely likes or finds fulfilling.
		Curiosity	The desire to learn about or explore something new.
		Problem Solving	The drive to or enjoyment of tackling challenges and finding their solutions.
		Sense of Belonging	The desire to belong to a particular group, or an existing sense of belonging within a particular group.
		Self-Efficacy	The belief in one's own ability to successfully do something.
	Intrinsic and Extrinsic Motivation	Impact	The desire to help others or to make meaningful changes in the world.

	Extrinsic Motivation	Avoiding Alternatives	Making a choice to avoid other, less favorable alternatives.
		Personal/ Career Goals	Ambitions or aspirations related to one's occupation or desired outcomes.
		External Validation	Refers to seeking positive recognition from others.
		Education Alignment	Following a perceived 'natural' path from education to career.
Challenges in Software Engineering	Barriers to Belonging	Individual Barriers	Refers to personal difficulties or internal struggles that affect a person's well-being or confidence.
		Systemic Barriers	Challenges faced which stem from obstacles built into policies, systems, and social structures.
		Social Barriers	Challenges that stem from difficulty working with or connecting with others.

	Technical Training Challenges	Academic Setbacks	Challenges within an academic journey, that hinder progress or achievement.
		Theory-Practice Gap	A lack of understanding for the connection between the content being taught in an educational setting and the intended use in practice.
		Pedagogical Challenges	Difficulties involving learning, including teachers, the learning environment, and the content.
	Career-Progression Challenges	Curriculum-Workplace Misalignment	The gap that exists between what is taught in educational programs and the skillset/knowledge required for the career.
		Job Search Struggles	Challenges faced by individuals when seeking employment.
		Navigating the Corporate Workplace	Difficulties with adapting to/understanding the expectations and dynamics within professional environments.

		Work Environment	Challenges with the physical or cultural setting of the workplace.
	Threats to Motivation	Lack of Challenging Work	Represents the experience of having tasks that are too simple, repetitive, or not engaging enough.
		Lack of Impact Visibility	Meaning the inability to see the impact or added value of the work that one is doing.
		Work-Interest Mismatch	Refers to a divide between one's interests within the field and the work they are required to do.